

SWXAI: A Unified Multimodal Explainability System for Space Weather Forecasting and
Heliophysics

by

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ABSTRACT

Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) is increasingly important in scientific machine learning, where transparency is needed to validate predictions, diagnose model behavior, and support scientific interpretation. In space weather forecasting and heliophysics, machine-learning workflows often span multiple modalities: solar images, multivariate time series, and tabular event-level data. However, explainability workflows for these modalities are often fragmented across libraries, model interfaces, and data formats, making them difficult to reuse, extend, and reproduce. We present SWXAI, a unified multimodal explainability resource providing a consistent interface for generating explanations across image, time-series, and tabular workflows. SWXAI supports gradient-based explainers for PyTorch models and

model-agnostic explainers for classical estimators, and bridges deep-learning and classical machine-learning pipelines through common validation, adaptation, and persistence layers. The repository also includes curated lightweight datasets, generation scripts, metadata, examples, and documentation so that users can run and extend multimodal explanation workflows without first reconstructing large external data pipelines.

INDEX WORDS: Solar flares, Space weather, Machine learning, Neural networks, Explainable artificial intelligence, Solar active regions, Heliophysics, Magnetograms, Geomagnetic storms, Coronal mass ejections, Time series analysis, Feature importance, Solar wind, Solar Dynamics Observatory, Classification

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is increasingly used in space weather forecasting and heliophysics for tasks such as solar flare prediction, active-region characterization, image-based solar analysis, and event-level geophysical studies (Angryk et al. 2020; Pandey et al. 2024; Ji et al. 2022; Bobra et al. 2014). As these models become part of scientific workflows, explainability becomes essential. Researchers need to understand which spatial regions, temporal intervals, or input variables are driving a prediction—not only whether a model performs well.

Despite this need, explainability workflows remain fragmented across data modalities and model ecosystems. Image explainability is handled with tensor-based tools, time-series explainability requires custom treatment of temporal structure and estimator interfaces, and tabular explainability is implemented through separate libraries. This fragmentation leads to duplicated engineering effort, inconsistent outputs, and limited reusability—creating a clear challenge in heliophysics, where a single research pipeline may span image, temporal, and structured data.

To address this gap, we present SWXAI, a unified multimodal explainability resource for space weather forecasting and heliophysics. SWXAI provides a common front-end interface for explanation generation across image, time-series, and tabular data, supporting both gradient-based explainers for PyTorch models and model-agnostic explainers for classical estimators. The main contributions are:

1. A unified explainability resource for image, time-series, and tabular scientific workflows.

2. Cross-backend support spanning PyTorch-based neural models and sklearn/AEON-style estimators.
3. Integrated explanation generation, validation, model adaptation, output persistence, and reusable artifacts.
4. Representative heliophysics datasets, runnable examples, tests, and documentation for reproducible use.
5. A practical software foundation for interpretable machine learning in space weather forecasting.

1.1 Background and Motivation

Space weather events—including solar flares, coronal mass ejections, and geomagnetic storms—can disrupt satellite operations, power grids, and communications systems. Accurate forecasting of these events requires processing large volumes of heterogeneous observational data, including solar images, active-region time series, and event catalogs. Machine learning has become a central tool in this domain, enabling automated pattern recognition across modalities and timescales.

As machine-learning models are increasingly deployed in scientific contexts, stakeholders—including researchers, forecasters, and domain experts—require not only accurate predictions but also explanations of how those predictions are made. Explainability supports model validation, scientific discovery, and trust in automated systems. In space weather, where model errors can have real-world consequences, interpretability is especially important.

The challenge is that no single explainability tool covers the full spectrum of models and data types used in heliophysics. PyTorch-based deep learning models require gradient-based attribution methods, while classical estimators such as Random Forests and XGBoost need model-agnostic black-box approaches. Each modality—image, time series, tabular—also requires different preprocessing and output formats. SWXAI was designed specifically to bridge these gaps in a single, reusable, reproducible package.

1.2 Related Work

Several well-established libraries address parts of the explainability ecosystem. Captum (Kokhlikyan et al. 2020) provides an interpretability framework for PyTorch models. SHAP (Lundberg & Lee 2017) and LIME (Ribeiro et al. 2016) are widely used for feature-attribution and local explanation workflows. aeon (Middlehurst et al. 2024) provides a unified framework for time-series learning. These tools are powerful and widely adopted, but scientific users working with multimodal heliophysics pipelines often need to combine them manually, leading to repeated engineering effort, inconsistent outputs, and limited reusability.

In practice, image explainability assumes tensor-based workflows with gradient access, while time-series workflows may rely on sklearn- or aeon-style estimators rather than deep networks. Tabular workflows introduce yet another library and output format. Researchers frequently build custom wrappers to bridge these gaps, slowing experimentation and reducing reproducibility. SWXAI addresses this need by packaging domain-grounded explanation methods with practical interfaces, adapters, examples, and reusable heliophysics outputs.

CHAPTER 2

SWXAI FRAMEWORK OVERVIEW

SWXAI is implemented as a Python package with a unified public interface centered on a front-end explainer object, `SpaceWeatherExplainer`. A user specifies an explanation method, modality, and task, and the framework dispatches the request to the appropriate backend. This design hides modality-specific and backend-specific complexity while keeping the framework extensible.

SWXAI consists of five main components: (1) a Unified API Layer exposed through `SpaceWeatherExplainer` that routes each request by method, modality, and task; (2) a Registry and Dispatch Layer that organizes explanation methods by name, decoupling the API from implementations; (3) a Validation and Adaptation Layer that normalizes inputs and bridges PyTorch (Paszke et al. 2019) versus sklearn/AEON (Pedregosa et al. 2011) estimators; (4) an Explanation Object and Persistence Layer that packages attribution values, metadata, and figures into reusable artifacts; and (5) Feature and Modeling Utilities supporting time-series feature extraction.

Figure 2.1 shows the overall system architecture, illustrating how multimodal inputs flow through the unified `SpaceWeatherExplainer` API, through the registry and validation layers, to backend model support, and finally to reusable explanation outputs.

Figure 2.1: Overview of the SWXAI architecture showing multimodal inputs, the unified SpaceWeatherExplainer API, registry and validation layers, backend model support, and reusable explanation outputs.

2.1 Unified API Layer

The `SpaceWeatherExplainer` class is the primary entry point for all SWXAI workflows. It accepts three key arguments: `method` (the name of the explanation algorithm to use), `modality` (one of `image`, `timeseries`, or `tabular`), and `task` (such as `classification` or `regression`). This uniform interface allows users to switch explanation methods or modalities without restructuring their code.

The API is intentionally minimal:

```
from swxai import SpaceWeatherExplainer as E

expl = E(method="shap_tabular",
         modality="tabular",
         task="classification")

out = expl.explain(clf, x_test, target=1)
```

2.2 Registry and Dispatch Layer

The registry pattern decouples the public API from method implementations. Each explainer is registered by name and retrieved dynamically. New methods can be added to the registry without modifying existing code, making the framework straightforward to extend.

2.3 Validation and Adaptation Layer

For PyTorch-based workflows, the framework converts inputs into tensors, validates shapes, and checks model-input compatibility. For non-PyTorch estimators, SWXAI exposes prediction-function interfaces suitable for black-box explainers, allowing users to switch between model classes without rewriting the explanation pipeline.

2.4 Explanation Object and Persistence Layer

The standardized explanation object packages attribution values, metadata, and figures into a consistent container. This allows outputs to be saved, reloaded, compared, and shared

across sessions and experiments—supporting reproducibility at the workflow level, not just at the model level.

2.5 Feature and Modeling Utilities

SWXAI also provides a suite of utilities for time-series feature extraction, including MiniRocket (Dempster et al. 2021), Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), SFA-Fast (Schäfer 2015), TSFresh (Christ et al. 2018), and RSAST (He et al. 2024). These utilities connect directly to the time-series explanation backend, enabling feature-based classifiers to be trained and explained through the same unified interface.

Figure 2.2 summarizes the full coverage of supported modalities, explanation methods, extensions, and utility resources across the SWXAI system.

Figure 2.2: SWXAI coverage across supported modalities, explanation methods, extensions, and utility and reproducibility resources.

2.6 Supported Modalities and Methods

SWXAI supports explainability across the main data types encountered in heliophysics while preserving a consistent interface across model families.

2.6.1 Image Modality

SWXAI supports gradient-based and perturbation-based explainers for PyTorch (Paszke et al. 2019) models: Integrated Gradients (Sundararajan et al. 2017), Saliency (Simonyan et al. 2014), SmoothGrad (Smilkov et al. 2017), Occlusion (Zeiler & Fergus 2014), and Grad-CAM-style methods (Selvaraju et al. 2017). These methods provide spatial attribution over image-like inputs, including solar observations commonly used in heliophysics workflows (Bobra et al. 2014).

2.6.2 Time-Series Modality

SWXAI supports gradient-based explainers for PyTorch time-series models and model-agnostic occlusion-based explanations for sklearn/AEON classifiers (Middlehurst et al. 2024; Pedregosa et al. 2011). The framework includes Slim-TSF (Ji et al. 2024), a custom interval-based component with swappable base estimators such as Random Forest (Breiman 2001), Extra Trees, and XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin 2016), and a configurable Time Series Transformer Classifier (Zerveas et al. 2021) for attention-based attribution. The feature-extraction utilities described in Section 2.5 can also be used with time-series classifiers and explanation workflows.

2.6.3 Tabular Modality

For tabular workflows, SWXAI supports SHAP (Lundberg & Lee 2017), LIME (Ribeiro et al. 2016), Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) (Goldstein et al. 2015), and Ceteris Paribus profiles (Biecek & Burzykowski 2021) for event-level analyses in geophysical settings.

CHAPTER 3

DATASETS AND REPOSITORY PREPARATION

A central part of SWXAI is that it does not only provide explanation methods, but also includes representative heliophysics datasets that make the package runnable, testable, and reproducible. The repository contains three lightweight datasets covering the three supported modalities: image, time-series, and tabular data. These datasets were selected to demonstrate realistic space-weather workflows while keeping the repository small enough for users to clone, install, and run examples without requiring access to the full-scale original archives.

Table 3.1 summarizes the three bundled datasets, their modalities, the scale of the bundled subset, and their role within the SWXAI framework.

Table 3.1: Bundled datasets and their role in SWXAI.

Dataset	Modality	Bundled Subset	Purpose
HMI AR-Patches	Image	150 balanced images; 2000-image larger subset	Spatial attribution over active-region magnetograms
SWAN-SF	Time Series	300 CSV windows across five partitions	Temporal and feature-level explanation for flare forecasting
Geomagnetic Storms	Tabular	132 events, 21 columns	Event-level SHAP, LIME, ICE, and CP explanations

3.1 HMI Active-Region Patch Dataset

The image workflow is based on active-region patch data derived from SDO/HMI line-of-sight magnetogram observations (Bobra et al. 2014). The original HMI active-region patch data are large-scale solar image datasets associated with active-region identifiers, observation times,

and flare-related metadata. These data are useful for image-based solar flare prediction and active-region analysis because they preserve spatial magnetic-field structure around solar active regions.

For SWXAI, a curated subset was prepared and bundled with the repository. The repository includes metadata files and compressed image subsets so that users can run image explanation examples without downloading the full original dataset. The smaller subset contains 150 images balanced across flare and non-flare classes, while the larger subset contains 2000 images spanning multiple GOES flare classes and non-flare examples. The sampling process was designed to preserve active-region diversity rather than simply taking arbitrary files. In particular, the subset construction script samples across HARP active-region identifiers and flare-class groups, helping avoid a dataset dominated by repeated images from only a few regions.

This preparation effort makes the image modality practical for demonstration and testing. It allows SWXAI to show spatial attribution methods such as occlusion and Grad-CAM-style explanations on real solar magnetogram data while keeping the repository lightweight and reproducible.

3.2 SWAN-SF Multivariate Time-Series Dataset

The time-series workflow is based on the SWAN-SF solar flare forecasting dataset (Angryk et al. 2020), which provides multivariate time-series samples derived from solar active-region parameters. The full SWAN-SF dataset is substantially larger and is organized into flare and

non-flare cases across multiple partitions. Each sample represents a temporal window of solar active-region measurements, making it suitable for testing time-series classification models and temporal explanation methods.

For SWXAI, a compact representative subset of SWAN-SF was created and stored in the repository. The included subset contains 300 CSV files across five partitions, with 30 flare and 30 non-flare samples selected from each partition. Each sample keeps the original multivariate temporal structure, including fixed-length windows, multiple physical features, and a 12-minute cadence. The subset-generation script also records metadata in an index file, including partition, label, file path, active-region information, and timing information.

The purpose of this subset is not to replace the full SWAN-SF benchmark, but to make time-series explainability examples easy to reproduce. It supports demonstration of temporal feature importance, model-agnostic occlusion, feature-based classifiers, and future extensions such as attention-based explanations for sequence models.

3.3 Geomagnetic Storms Tabular Dataset

The tabular workflow uses a curated geomagnetic storm event dataset derived from the NASA CDAW intense geomagnetic storms catalog (NASA CDAW Data Center 2026). The original catalog contains storm-level records with information about Dst intensity, storm type, solar source location, solar wind properties, magnetic-field measurements, and related event characteristics. These variables provide a compact event-level representation that is suitable for tabular classification and feature-attribution methods.

In the SWXAI repository, the processed CSV contains 132 storm events and 21 columns. The included script parses the source storm records, cleans missing or irregular values, converts numeric fields, extracts solar source latitude and longitude, and computes derived fields such as propagation time. The resulting dataset includes CME, SIR, and CMESIR storm types and supports SHAP, LIME, ICE, and Ceteris Paribus explanations.

This dataset was included because it complements the image and time-series datasets with a structured event-level modality. Together, the three datasets allow SWXAI to demonstrate a consistent explainability interface across spatial, temporal, and tabular heliophysics data.

3.4 Dataset Preparation Effort and Reproducibility

Preparing these datasets required additional engineering beyond simply placing files in the repository. The original datasets are large, heterogeneous, and organized in different formats, so each modality required a separate preparation pipeline. For image data, the work involved selecting representative HMI active-region patches, preserving class information, maintaining metadata, and packaging image archives. For SWAN-SF, the work involved constructing a balanced undersampled time-series subset across partitions while preserving temporal structure and labels. For the geomagnetic storm dataset, the work involved parsing and cleaning event records, standardizing fields, and producing a compact tabular CSV with a data dictionary.

These preparation steps are important because SWXAI is intended to be a reusable software resource. By including curated datasets, metadata, and generation scripts, the repository

allows users to inspect how the examples were created, rerun the dataset preparation process, and extend the framework to larger or alternative datasets. This makes the project stronger as a resource because the examples are not isolated figures—they are tied to reproducible data preparation workflows.

The repository organization also makes the data preparation auditable. Each dataset directory contains a short description of the subset and, where applicable, the script used to build or refresh it. For example, the HMI active-region directory includes metadata for both the 150-image and 2000-image subsets, the SWAN-SF directory documents the balanced toy subset across five partitions, and the geomagnetic-storm directory includes both the generated CSV and a data dictionary. These supporting files help future users distinguish between the original scientific datasets, the compact versions bundled for demonstration, and the processing choices made to make the examples runnable in a lightweight repository.

CHAPTER 4

IMPLEMENTATION AND REPRODUCIBILITY

This chapter describes how the SWXAI framework is realized as an installable and reproducible software package. While Chapter 2 introduced the main framework layers conceptually, this chapter focuses on the repository structure, package organization, examples, tests, documentation, dependency management, and saved artifacts that make the framework runnable and extensible.

The implementation is designed to support lightweight end-to-end use. Users can install the package from the repository, run example workflows for each modality, inspect bundled data subsets and metadata, and save explanation outputs for later comparison. This organization helps separate scientific workflows from implementation details while preserving a clear path for adding new methods, models, and datasets.

4.1 Package Organization

The SWXAI repository is organized as follows. The top-level package exposes `SpaceWeatherExplainer` as the main public interface. Submodules cover each modality—image, time series, tabular—and each submodule registers its own set of supported explainers with the central registry. A shared utilities submodule provides common functionality such as tensor conversion, estimator adaptation, and persistence helpers.

The examples directory contains runnable Python scripts for the supported workflows, while the notebooks directory contains starter and multimodal demonstration notebooks. Together, these files show each modality end-to-end, from data loading through model

training and explanation generation. The tests directory provides smoke tests for the registry, image attribution, tabular explainers, AEON-style model-agnostic time-series occlusion, and Slim-TSF utilities. Documentation is provided via docstrings and a dedicated docs directory, covering installation, the public API, supported methods, outputs, and dataset usage.

4.2 Cross-Backend Support

One of the key technical challenges in building SWXAI was providing a uniform interface across radically different model backends. PyTorch models expose gradients and support forward-pass hooks, which are necessary for gradient-based attribution methods. Sklearn and AEON estimators expose `predict` and `predict_proba` interfaces but do not support gradient computation.

SWXAI resolves this through an adaptation layer that wraps non-PyTorch estimators in a prediction-function interface. This wrapper is compatible with model-agnostic explainers such as SHAP and LIME, which only require the ability to call the model on arbitrary inputs. For PyTorch models, the adaptation layer ensures tensor shapes and dtypes match model expectations before calling gradient-based methods.

4.3 Explanation Persistence

Explanation outputs in SWXAI are packaged into a standardized `Explanation` object. This object stores the raw attribution array, a summary dictionary describing the explanation run, and any generated figures. The object can save artifacts such as `attributions.npy`, `summary.json`, and figure files, allowing explanations to be archived, shared, and compared

across experiments without rerunning the full pipeline.

This persistence capability is particularly important for reproducibility. In many research workflows, regenerating explanations requires retraining models and re-running preprocessing pipelines. By storing the explanation artifact independently, SWXAI allows researchers to revisit and compare results without this overhead.

4.4 Testing and Validation

SWXAI includes a test suite that validates the main package routes across all three modalities and both model backends. Unit and smoke tests verify registry imports, image Integrated Gradients output shapes, tabular ICE and Ceteris Paribus grids, AEON-style model-agnostic time-series occlusion, and Slim-TSF fitting and feature-generation behavior. These tests emphasize reproducible package behavior and backend compatibility rather than claiming benchmark-level model performance.

Validation of explanation quality is an open challenge in interpretable machine learning, as ground truth for what constitutes a “correct” explanation is rarely available. SWXAI addresses this pragmatically by testing shape consistency, finite outputs, successful serialization, and stable execution across representative model classes. A dedicated metrics module is also included as a foundation for future faithfulness and stability checks.

4.5 Code Availability

The source code for SWXAI is publicly available in the project repository. The repository includes all modular components, bundled datasets, runnable examples, and documentation

needed to reproduce the results presented in this report:

`https://bitbucket.org/gsudmlab/swxai/src/main/`

All code is written in Python and follows standard packaging conventions. The repository uses `pyproject.toml` to declare core dependencies and optional extras such as AEON, Captum, Grad-CAM, and feature-extraction support. Installation can therefore be performed from the repository root using standard editable-install commands such as `pip install -e .`, with optional extras added as needed for specific workflows.

CHAPTER 5

REPRESENTATIVE OUTPUTS

Figures 5.1–5.3 present representative SWXAI outputs across image, time-series, and tabular modalities using the bundled heliophysics datasets, illustrating modality-specific explanations through a unified interface.

5.1 Image Modality — HMI Magnetogram

Figure 5.1 shows an occlusion-based explanation on an HMI active-region magnetogram. A convolutional neural network (CNN) was trained on the image subset and SWXAI generated the explanation for a sample prediction. The heatmap highlights spatial regions contributing most strongly to the model output. The attribution pattern reveals which portions of the magnetogram encode the most discriminative magnetic-field structure for flare classification.

Figure 5.1: Occlusion-based spatial attribution on an HMI active-region magnetogram. The heatmap highlights regions contributing most strongly to the prediction.

5.2 Time-Series Modality — SWAN-SF

Figure 5.2 shows temporal importance scores for a SWAN-SF multivariate solar flare sample. A Random Forest classifier was trained and SWXAI’s time-series pipeline generated the feature importance visualization using model-agnostic occlusion, systematically masking intervals across each feature channel and measuring the resulting drop in classification

probability. TOTUSJH shows the strongest importance growth near the end of the 700-minute observation window, consistent with the physical expectation that magnetic helicity accumulation immediately preceding a flare is a strong predictor.

Figure 5.2: Temporal importance scores for a SWAN-SF multivariate sample. TOTUSJH, MEANSHR, and R_VALUE are shown as top contributing variables.

5.3 Tabular Modality — Geomagnetic Storms

Figure 5.3 shows a SHAP-based explanation on the geomagnetic storms dataset. In this representative run, propagation time and solar wind speed at shock receive the highest mean absolute SHAP values for severe-storm classification. These results are physically

interpretable: shorter propagation times and higher solar wind speeds are associated with more intense geomagnetic storms in the observational literature.

Figure 5.3: SHAP-based feature attribution on the geomagnetic storms dataset. Propagation time and solar wind speed at shock show the highest mean absolute SHAP values.

5.4 Cross-Modality Consistency

An important property of the SWXAI system is that despite the very different nature of these three explanation outputs—spatial heatmaps, temporal importance curves, and SHAP bar charts—they are all generated through the same API call pattern. The user specifies a method and modality, calls `explain`, and receives a standardized output object. This consistency

substantially reduces the engineering burden of building multi-modal explainability workflows and ensures that outputs are stored, compared, and visualized in a uniform way.

This consistency also makes the representative outputs easier to extend. A user can replace the sample model, switch from one supported explainer to another, or move from the lightweight bundled subsets to larger external datasets while keeping the surrounding workflow largely unchanged. In this sense, Figures 5.1–5.3 are not isolated visual examples; they demonstrate the intended core design of SWXAI: modality-specific explanations produced through a common interface and returned as reusable artifacts.

CHAPTER 6

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

6.1 Discussion

SWXAI occupies a practical middle ground between general-purpose explainability libraries and domain-specific scientific workflows. Rather than replacing foundational tools such as Captum, SHAP, LIME, or aeon, it provides a unifying framework that helps researchers apply such methods consistently across multimodal heliophysics workflows—covering solar active-region image analysis, time-series classification, tabular event analysis, and feature-based baselines—while standardizing interfaces and outputs.

The registry-based architecture and consistent explanation objects substantially reduce repeated engineering effort and improve cross-workflow reproducibility. The current release focuses on reusable system integration rather than proposing new standalone explanation algorithms.

The bundled datasets also play an important role in making SWXAI reproducible. Rather than requiring users to manually locate, download, and preprocess large external datasets before testing the package, SWXAI includes compact curated subsets with preparation scripts and metadata. This design makes the framework easier to evaluate, teach, and extend. It also demonstrates how the same explanation interface can be applied across realistic heliophysics data types without requiring users to rewrite modality-specific preprocessing and explanation code.

The current resource is intentionally lightweight. This makes it practical for demonstrations

and examples, but it also means that benchmark-scale training, large-scale ablation studies, and rigorous explanation evaluation remain areas for future expansion. SWXAI should therefore be viewed as a software and reproducibility foundation that can grow into a broader community resource.

6.2 Conclusion

We presented SWXAI, a unified multimodal explainability resource for space weather forecasting and heliophysics. SWXAI provides a consistent interface for generating explanations across image, time-series, and tabular workflows, supporting both deep-learning and classical machine-learning estimators. By combining explanation methods, model adaptation, feature utilities, reusable outputs, and representative datasets, SWXAI reduces engineering overhead and supports reproducible interpretability workflows for heterogeneous scientific data.

The framework’s registry-based design and standardized explanation objects make it straightforward to integrate new methods, extend existing modalities, and maintain consistency across backends. Together with the bundled datasets and generation scripts, SWXAI provides a practical, self-contained foundation that researchers can clone, run, and build upon without reconstructing external data pipelines. We believe this combination of a clean API, cross-backend support, and curated reproducible datasets positions SWXAI as a useful long-term resource for interpretable machine learning in the space weather and heliophysics community.

6.3 Future Work

Future work will expand SWXAI along several directions. On the data side, additional datasets spanning further heliophysics domains and prediction tasks will continue to be added as the resource grows. The initial three modalities are intended as a representative starting point, and future releases will broaden both the range of sources and the scale of bundled subsets.

On the methods side, SWXAI will be extended with a broader set of explanation techniques. Planned additions include counterfactual explanations, uncertainty quantification, concept-based explanations, domain-aware perturbation methods that respect physical structure, and additional gradient-based and attention-based explainers. Additional explanation methods will continue to be incorporated as the field advances.

Future versions will also improve explanation evaluation through quantitative faithfulness and stability metrics, and cross-method comparison tools. Finally, richer documentation, additional example notebooks, and easier integration with larger training pipelines will help move SWXAI toward a broader community resource for interpretable machine learning in space weather forecasting and heliophysics.

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